

```

install.packages("metafor")
library(metafor)

dataset <- escalc(measure="MD", m1i=Mean_Treatment, sd1i=SD_Treatment,
n1i=N_Treatment, m2i=Mean_Control, sd2i=SD_Control, n2i=N_Control, data=dat)

#EFFECT SIZE CALCULATION (MD, RANDOM EFFECT MODEL = REML)
meta <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML")
summary(meta, digits=3)

#SENSITIVITY AND PUBLICATION BIAS TEST
leave1out(meta)
trim.rf <- trimfill(meta)
trim.rf
funnel(trim.rf)
regtest(meta, predictor= "sei")

#META-REGRESSION (MIXED-EFFECT MODELS)
#Moderator dose
dose <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ dose, data=dataset)
summary(dose, digits=3)
dose1 <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ dose + I(dose^2), data=dataset)
summary(dose1, digits=8)

#moderator treatment duration
dura <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ duration, data=dataset)
summary(dura, digits=3)

#moderator initial age
age <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ age, data=dataset)
summary(age, digits=3)

#moderator initial form
form <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ form, data=dataset)
summary(form, digits=3)

#SUBGROUP ANALYSIS
#Treatment duration
duration1 <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML", subset=(duration=="less than 4"))
duration1

duration2 <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML", subset=(duration=="less than 8"))
duration2

duration3 <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML", subset=(duration=="more than 8"))

```

duration3

#Initial age

```
age1 <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML", subset=(age=="less than 50"))  
age1
```

```
age2 <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML", subset=(age=="more than 50"))  
age2
```

#Quercetin form

```
form1 <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML", subset=(form=="extract"))  
form1
```

```
form2 <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method = "REML", subset=(form=="plant powder"))  
form2
```